

AI Techniques for Cataract Detection : A Review

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Abstract—Cataracts are among the leading diseases that cause blindness around the world, emerging as one of the most common eye diseases. Traditional approaches for cataract diagnosis depends on the manual examination of patients by eye specialist doctors, which can be time consuming. Early detection and timely intervention are crucial to prevent vision loss. In recent years, more advanced deep learning algorithms such as Convolutional Neural Networks, VGG16, MobileNet, etc., are introduced into the medical imaging field to address these limitations. these algorithms provide a good advantage in fully automated cataract detection with high accuracy, rapidity and dependability. In this review paper, deep learning for cataract detection has been highlighted by comparing different algorithms for cataract detection. Alongside this, we discuss the advantages and disadvantages as well as the challenges and future directions of these algorithms. This paper aims to provide an introduction on the application of deep learning in cataract detection, making it accessible for both researchers and non-specialists interested in AI-driven healthcare solutions.

Index Terms—Cataract Detection, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks, Retinal Fundus Images, Artificial Intelligence

I. INTRODUCTION

When the proteins of the lens of the eyes degrade and clump together, then cataracts develop, which causes cloudiness of vision. The condition gradually increases, it decreases the clarity of vision, making everyday routine tasks such as reading or driving more and more difficult and thus considerably impairing the quality of life of the patient. Blindness due to cataracts is very common in low and middle-income countries where ophthalmology services are limited.

Traditional approaches in cataract diagnostics involve clinical examinations and imaging techniques that are resource-intensive and impractical for large-scale screening. With aging populations, their demand for cataract screening and treatment is expected to grow exponentially, leading to an unavoidable demand for scalable and efficient diagnostic methods.

As a result, deep learning has emerged as a life-changing technology in medical imaging because it allows the scope of automated analysis of very complicated datasets with high precision. Applications most commonly used for the image classification task including the detection of diseases from retinal images, have been convolutional neural networks and their alternatives including MobileNet, VGG-16 etc. These models analyze visual patterns and features in normal or retinal images

to identify abnormalities associated with cataract, offering an alternative method that automates the traditional diagnostic approach. This paper aims to apply these models in developing a cataract detection system through pre-processing normal or retinal eye images, training the models against labeled datasets and evaluating the models based on the evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision and recall. This review paper will cover the fundamental aspects of cataract detection using machine learning and deep learning approaches.

II. OPHTHALMIC IMAGING MODALITIES FOR CATARACT CLASSIFICATION

Accurate cataract diagnosis relies on clear and informative images of the eye. Several imaging modalities are commonly used for this purpose, each offering unique advantages and disadvantages:

A. Slit Lamp Images

Slit lamp biomicroscopy provides excellent high-resolution detailed images of the anterior segment of the eye including the lens. These pictures are marketed for cataract classification and evaluation as they showcase subtle opacities and clarity in the lenses. However, these images are acquired with special equipment using trained personnel.

B. Fundus Images

Fundus images represent photographs taken with specially equipped cameras to reveal the entire posterior segment of the eye, including the retina and optic nerve. The images do not show the lens directly as do the slit lamp photographs; however, indirect evidence of a cataract is often manifest by altered illumination or reflections from the retina.

C. Digital Camera Images

Digital images obtained from the ordinary digital cameras usually with additional lenses or adapters are easily accessible and cheap means of acquiring images. However, they may not be of the best quality, as compared to what can be obtained via specialized ophthalmic imaging devices, and thus may limit accuracy in automated cataract detection.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Waleed F. Faris et al. [1] focuses on developing an automatic cataract detection system by integrating deep learning-based feature extraction with classification techniques. The dataset used in this study is collected through an IoT module from a public health dataset and includes regular eye images. The research employs K Neural Networks for preprocessing and deep-region neural networks for classification. The study demonstrates that this method improves early cataract detection and classification.

Fan Gan et al. [2] discusses AI-based cataract staging using anterior segment images. The dataset consists of 647 high-quality anterior segment images categorized into four stages: incipient, intumescent, mature and hypermature. The study uses FCNResNet50 for segmentation and SVM for classification. Deep transfer learning with multi-feature fusion significantly enhances the accuracy of cortical cataract staging. A manual segmentation-based platform achieved an accuracy of 97.48% for training and 90.00% for testing.

Halit ÇETİNER et al. [3] explores the classification of cataract disease using deep learning models based on transfer learning. The research uses the Ocular Disease Intelligent Recognition (ODIR) dataset that contains fundus images for classification. The study compares the performance of MobileNet-V3 Small with the proposed MobileNet-V3 model, resulting in an improved test accuracy of 97%, demonstrating the potential of lightweight, high-accuracy classification models.

Nikhil Panjwani et al. [4] uses a 16-layer CNN optimized for cataract detection using fundus images. The dataset combines HRF, FIRE, IDRiD and DRIVE datasets, containing 1,130 cataract-affected and 1,130 normal images. The proposed CNN model is lightweight and achieved an accuracy of 99.13%, outperforming pre-trained models like VGG16, VGG19 and ResNet50.

He Xie et al. [5] uses a deep learning system for detecting visually impaired cataracts using 8,395 fundus images. The dataset is categorized into three non-cataract, mild cataract and visually impaired cataract classes. DenseNet121 outperformed ResNet50 and Inception-v3 in classification accuracy.

Masum Shah Junayed et al. [6] build CataractNet for an automated cataract detection system based on deep learning. The dataset consists of 1,130 fundus images, which are expanded using augmentation techniques to 4,746 images. The model is compared with VGG16, VGG19, MobileNet, Inception-v3 and ResNet50. CataractNet achieved the highest accuracy of 99.13%, proving its efficiency in automated cataract detection.

Md Kamrul Hasan et al. [7] explores transfer learning-based methods for cataract detection using 1,088 fundus images. The research compares models like DenseNet121, Xception, InceptionV3 and InceptionResNetV2. InceptionResNetV2 achieved the highest accuracy of 98.17%, showing the effectiveness of transfer learning in reducing training time while maintaining high performance.

Shivam Kumar Upadhyay et al. [8] develops a deep learning-based detection system using CNN and Random For-

est. The Kaggle dataset consists of 245 cataract, 246 normal images for training and 61 cataract, 60 normal images for testing are used. The CNN model achieved a classification accuracy of 97.67%, outperforming the Random Forest model.

Hera Dwi Novita et al. [9] compares CNN, K-Nearest Neighbors and SVM for cataract detection. The dataset includes eye images captured using smartphones and slit-lamp cameras. The CNN model achieved an accuracy of 95.31%, significantly outperforming SVM (86.39%) and KNN (85.34%). The study concludes that CNNs provide superior accuracy and efficiency compared to traditional machine learning models.

P. N. Senthil Prakash et al. [10] develops CataractsNET, a lightweight CNN model for cataract detection. The dataset contains 9,600 augmented images. CataractsNET achieved an accuracy of 96.20%, outperforming ResNet50 and VGG19. .

Sarah Agustin et al. [11] develops a CNN-based cataract detection system using 4000 grayscale eye images. Preprocessing includes data augmentation techniques to enhance the model's generalization. The model achieved an accuracy of 94.8% showing its reliability in early cataract detection.

S.B. Saleema Parvin et al. [12] introduces a hybrid approach combining CNN with Autoencoder for cataract detection. The CNN model combined with Autoencoder achieved an accuracy of 97.36% for the right eye and 92.84% for the left eye. The study shows the effectiveness of Autoencoder in improving classification performance.

Pradeep Mullangi et al. [13] uses pre-trained CNN models for automated cataract detection. It shows that DenseNet-121 outperformed other models, achieving an accuracy of 92%. The study introduces CatCNNNet, which integrates DenseNet and ResNet features with attention mechanisms.

Lahari P. L. et al. [14] developed CSDNet, a lightweight deep learning framework for cataract detection. Using the ODIR dataset, CSDNet achieved high accuracy while minimizing computational requirements, making it suitable for resource-constrained environments.

Irshad Khan et al. [15] examined the use of ResNet-50 for cataract detection. ResNet-50 fine-tuned with transfer learning achieved high classification accuracy showing its applicability in mobile and clinical settings. Salwa Shakir Mahmood et al. [16] improved automated cataract detection through transfer learning with ResNet-50. The dataset includes fundus images from 5000 patients. The study shows the benefits of transfer learning in improving classification performance while reducing computational costs.

Thittaporn Ganokratanaa et al. [17] uses a lightweight LeNet-CNN model for cataract detection. It achieved an accuracy of 96% outperforming SVM and decision tree models.

Behnam Askarian et al. [18] develops a smartphone-based cataract detection system using luminance-based image analysis and SVM. The model achieved 96.6% accuracy, showing its potential for mobile healthcare applications.

TABLE I: Cataract Detection Study Summary

Author(s)	Dataset	Algorithms	Accuracy
Waleed F. Faris (2020) [1]	Dataset has been collected through the IOT module from the public health dataset.	K- NEURAL NETWORK, Deep Region Neural Network	K-NeuNet & De-RegNN = 95%
Fan Gan et al. (2023) [2]	647 high-quality anterior segment images (Slit lamp)	FCNResNet50, SVM	SVM = 97.48% (manual segmentation), 94.59% (automatic segmentation)
Halit ÇETİNER (2023) [3]	ODIR dataset (5000 fundus images, 1088 selected)	MobileNetV3 small, Proposed MobileNetV3	MobileNetV3 = 97%, MobileNetV3 Small = 89%
Nikhil Panjwani et al. (2023) [4]	1130 cataract and 1130 normal eye fundus images	Custom 16-layer CNN, VGG16, VGG19, ResNet50	Custom CNN = 99.13%
He Xie et al. (2023) [5]	8395 fundus images (3569 non-cataract, 3245 mild, 1581 severe)	DenseNet121, ResNet50, Inception-v3	DenseNet121 = 97.3% (non-cataract), 85.5% (mild), 88.2% (severe)
Masum Shah Junayed et al. (2021) [6]	1130 cataract fundus images, extended to 4746 images	CataractNet, VGG-16, VGG-19, MobileNet, Inception-v3, ResNet-50	CataractNet = 99.13%
Md Kamrul Hasan et al. (2023) [7]	1088 fundus images, ODIR dataset	DenseNet121, Xception, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2	InceptionResNetV2 = 98.17%
Shivam Kumar Upadhyay et al. (2024) [8]	Dataset from Kaggle is used. 245 cataract and 246 normal images for training. 61 cataract and 60 normal images for testing.	CNN, Random Forest	CNN = 97.67%, RF = 92.44%
Hera Dwi Novita et al. (2024) [9]	1159 normal eye images from smartphones and slit-lamp cameras	CNN, KNN, SVM	CNN = 95.31%, SVM = 86.39%, KNN = 85.34%
P. N. Senthil Prakash et al. (2024) [10]	9000 images (google and augmented); 8000 training, 1600 testing	CNN, CataractsNET, VGG19, ResNet50	CataractsNET = 96.20%, ResNet50 = 95%, VGG19 = 92.5%
Sarah Agustin et al. (2024) [11]	4000 eye images (70% training, 20% validation, 10% testing)	CNN	CNN = 94.8%
S.B. Saleema Parvin et al. (2024) [12]	6392 fundus images from 5000 patients	CNN-AE, Inception-V2	CNN-AE = 97.36% (right eye), 92.84% (left eye)
Pradeep Mullangi et al. (2024) [13]	1130 fundus images (565 cataract, 565 normal); augmented to 4746 images	MobileNet, VGG-16, VGG-19, DenseNet121, ResNet50, Inception-v3	DenseNet-121 = 92%
Lahari P. L., Ramesh Vaddi et al. (2024) [14]	ODIR dataset (5000 patients)	CSDNet (Custom CNN)	CSDNet = 98.17%
Irshad Khan, Wajahat Akbar et al. (2024) [15]	3500 fundus images (HRF, IDRiD, ACHIKO-I, ODIR datasets)	ResNet-50	ResNet-50 = 97.56% (full Cataract), 95.23% (partial Cataract)
Salwa Shakir Mahmood et al. (2024) [16]	Color fundus images from 5000 patients	ResNet-50 (Transfer Learning)	ResNet-50 = 96.58% (training), 96.63% (testing)
Thittaporn Ganokratanaa et al. (2023) [17]	Eye images from digital cameras	LeNet-CNN, SVM	LeNet-CNN = 96%, SVM = 92%
Behnam Askarian et al. (2021) [18]	100 eye images (50 normal, 50 cataract) captured via smartphone cameras	Luminance-based processing, SVM	SVM = 96.6%

IV. AI TECHNIQUES FOR CATARACT DETECTION

AI techniques have gained significant attention in cataract detection. Among AI techniques, deep learning algorithms have shown promising results in cataract detection.

A. Deep Learning Models

1) *Convolutional Neural Network* : Convolutional neural network is a deep learning model made to solve visual problems as in images. It can recognize patterns, edges and features in an image as the human brain processes visual information. Rather than treating it as a set of single pixels, it uses a convolutional layer filter, which scans the image using small sections to spot important features like edges, shapes and textures. This helps recognize patterns irrespective of their positions in an image. After the convolution process, non-linearity is introduced to the model to learn complicated patterns via activation function application such as ReLU. Pooling layers are then used to minimize the image dimension so that the model is also more efficient and is not aligned towards smallest variances. Finally fully connected layers process the extracted raw features and classify them into categories.

2) *VGG-16* : VGG-16 is a deep convolutional neural network architecture developed by members of Visual Geometry Group at the University of Oxford. The model has 16 layers with trainable parameters, mainly a composition of convolutional and fully connected layers. The intuition behind VGG-16 is the application of small 3x3 convolutional filters for multiple layers to capture the fine features of most parts while maintaining computational efficacy. The architecture follows a regular pattern whereby convolutional layers are stacked followed by max-pooling layers that down-sample spatial resolution yet contribute to the features. Subsequently, after a few convolutional and pooling layers, the final output is flattened and relayed to fully connected layers until it reaches the softmax layer for classification.

3) *ResNet50* : Residual Neural Network-50 is deep convolutional neural network created mainly for overcoming the vanishing gradient problem, a major obstacle in the training of very deep networks. The ResNet50 is developed at Microsoft Research rests on the concept of residual learning where the network learns not the full transformation from input to output but rather the residual(difference) between input and output, allowing the use of skip connections to bypass one or several layers and directly connect some of the earlier layers to some of the later ones. ResNet50 contains fifty layers of convolution, batch normalization, ReLU activations, max-pooling and fully connected layers. One of the most typical properties of ResNet-50 is the use of bottleneck blocks that reduces the demand for computational resources and maximizes deep feature extraction.

4) *MobileNet* : MobileNet is a limited-model Convolutional Neural Network designed specifically for mobile and embedded uses where computation efficiency and energy consumption are important. This framework is developed by Google aims to implement classification and detection systems

specialized for resource-constrained platforms. Rather than a single, large convolution operation, MobileNet first operates a depthwise convolution that filters each input channel individually, followed by a pointwise convolution that merges the filtered outputs. This leads to reduced computational cost while keeping up the accuracy under MobileNet.

B. Machine Learning Models

1) *Random Forest* : Random Forest is a machine learning technique for classification or regression tasks. The method represents a generalization for building many decision trees and averaging their results to improve accuracy and counter overfitting. Random Forest basically has a forest of decision trees that is created with each tree being trained on a random subset of the dataset using a technique called bootstrap aggregation. When training each tree only a random subset of features is considered for splitting at each node, thereby ensuring diversity in the trees so that they remain independent. After all trees have been trained, the predictions are averaged in the case of regression or determined using majority voting in the case of classification.

2) *K-Nearest Neighbors* : KNN is a machine learning algorithm that is simple and intuitive and is used for both classification and regression. The KNN algorithm works by finding K nearest data points or neighbors with respect to a metric such as Euclidean distance. In classification, the KNN algorithm assigns a class to a query point by taking that of its K nearest neighbors' most common class. while in regression, it averages their values.

3) *Support Vector Machine* : SVM is a machine learning algorithm that is used for classification task. It builds a hyperplane to separate the data points of different classes. The feature of this hyperplane is that it maximizes the margin. SVM can handle linear and nonlinear classification through the usage of several kernel functions like Radial Basis Function and Polynomial kernel by transforming the input data into a higher number of dimensions where linear separation is possible.

4) *Radial Basis Function Network* : RBFN is an artificial neural network for the purpose of classification or regression. The three layers are the input layer, hidden layer with radial basis functions such as Gaussian functions and the output layer. The function hidden layer assesses the degree of similarity between input data and the array of centers, supplying outputs that decrease as distance increases. The final prediction is then obtained by combining these outputs.

C. Hybrid Models

1) *CNN with self-organizing maps* : A CNN with Self-Organizing Map combines the feature extraction power of a CNN with the unsupervised learning capabilities of the SOM. Convolutional neural networks are mainly aimed at image processing through convolutional layers providing the detection of patterns while preserving important features. after such meaningful features are extracted using CNNs those

features will be analyzed and further clustered using Self-Organizing Map. Such a map will plot high-dimensional data onto some lower-dimensional grid and subsequent clustering within such a grid can naturally group data without any need for labeled data.

2) *CNN with Autoencoder* : A Convolutional Neural Network as an Autoencoder involves the feature extraction capabilities of CNN and the unsupervised learning of autoencoders. Convolutional layers are used here for pattern detection whereas pooling layers are used for reducing spatial dimensions while preserving important features. With the autoencoder, the features extracted pass through an architecture consisting of an encoder and decoder. The encoder compresses extracted features into a lower-dimensional representation, capturing essential information, and the decoder reconstructs the input.

3) *ResNet50 using Transfer Learning* : Transfer learning on ResNet50 uses the learned features of a trained ResNet50 model to be useful with other tasks. ResNet50 is a deep convolutional neural network trained on large datasets such as ImageNet and it learns through the hierarchy low-level patterns like edges, textures and shapes of an object. Instead of training a new model from the start, transfer learning reuses these features for the new dataset and usually requires fewer labeled examples and less time for training.

V. DATASETS

The availability and quality of datasets are crucial for training effective deep learning models:

A. Challenges in dataset diversity and availability

Many datasets are limited and may not cover the spectrum of cataract severity and patient demographic characteristics. Datasets are frequently skewed towards normal or cataract cases, leading to the model not being trained sufficiently. The poor acquisition of medical data leads to data scarcity. Different scenarios, including blurriness or inconsistent illumination lead to variability in image quality, which can affect the model's performance. Moreover, cataract diagnosis can also be subjective as it relies on the expertise or experience of the ophthalmologists who annotate the images. To fight these challenges, data preprocessing techniques, such as CLAHE and normalization, are applied to enhance image quality.

B. Data pre-processing and augmentation

These are crucial steps to make machine learning models for cataract detection strong enough to impact their accuracy and reliability. These steps consist of pre-processing techniques, including resizing the image to most commonly used size of 224x224-pixel. Contrast enhancement will be performed using a method called CLAHE to improve clarity in the images. Further normalization applied to scale and map the intensity values of pixels. In order to avoid overfitting and make the model as robust as possible, data augmentation techniques can be used, such as geometric transformations (rotation, flipping, scaling and cropping) to increase training dataset size and

variability. Image diversity may be enhanced further by using combinations of augmentation techniques, such as horizontal flips or rotations by some angles.

VI. FUTURE DIRECTIONS IN AI FOR CATARACT DETECTION

Future research is to make cataract detection models generalize better on diverse datasets by using techniques such as domain adaptation or federated learning. Multimodal imaging methods, including fundus photography, optical coherence tomography (OCT) and slit-lamp images can potentially be combined to yield better diagnostic outcomes. Further, lightweight AI models optimized for mobile and real-time applications will help in making cataract detection relevant to the field, especially in remote and under-resourced settings.

Explainable AI will help to provide explanation of model's decisions through visualizations, which furthers acceptance and build trust in AI-based approaches among clinicians. In addition, integrating AI into telemedicine platforms can facilitate early cataract screening and diagnosis allowing for timely medical intervention for underserved populations.

VII. CONCLUSION

Deep learning and machine learning algorithms improved the accuracy and efficiency of cataract detection to a great extent. CNN-based models are reported to classify with greater accuracy, especially using transfer learning techniques than traditional methods. Systems like DenseNet, ResNet and custom CNNs showed their strengths in different areas like in computational efficiency and effectively handling complex image patterns. Lightweight models like MobileNet is useful to run on a mobile or cloud platform, enabling AI-assisted medical solutions that provide greater accessibility to cataract screening in resource-poor areas. The use of CNN algorithm provides an efficient and automated approach for cataract detection, offering improved feature extraction and classification accuracy. CNN helps in early diagnosis due to the capacity to process complex pattern images and can be trusted on real-world applications.

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